

Community-based (e)participation: an ethical Social Protection trail

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1. Introduction

According to estimations, life expectancy is increasing, based on a global overview, despite some variations, caused by life cycle risks. In line with the increase of longevity, healthy life expectancy is also increasing [1]. These factors associated to others have been contributed to the increase of human population. On the other hand, as the life cycle advances, the possibilities of comorbidities increase and consequently also the level of dependence [2]. In parallel to these expected challenges associated to human life cycle, there are also others that test human ability to survive and adapt, such as planet life cycle and society challenges.

The human history reveals that coevolutionary approach can lead humanity to go further and challenge several obstacles [3] [4].

Despite all the progress that have been made, there is still a long trail to build and to benefit from. Statistics reveals only a part of the systems and, as in any system, there is always margin for improvement based on human needs and expectations. Anonymised data and associated metadata (with disaggregated variables of public datasets), open access, description of accessibility options (from data acquisition to data publication) and interoperability analysis based on human-centred approach are some of the challenges to face to access to the system-based performance.

These limitations, among others, can be a challenge for (e)participationⁱ of some groups of people, such as people with permanent or temporary specific needs. Digital divide is also a challenge of (e)participation considering the vision of pursue equityⁱⁱ for sustainability.

1.1. Motivation

Humans always faced big challenges related to interaction with the ecosystem, society and personal life cycle.

Focusing on society challenges, despite all the evolution, the current and known human relational challenges proves that humanity still has a long journey to do based on a vision of a trail to coevolutionary social sustainability. This is a reality across the world that no region of the planet is excluded. These challenges include several variables intrinsic to human life cycle, namely safety, security, social, self/status and success [5] [6] [7].

The called 5th generation era, marked by several buzzwords like Society 5.0, Industry 5.0, Education 5.0 and others, that are based on the human-centred approach, allow the virtual navigation through several tools that can potentiate the optimization of the route to reduce social exclusion and increase equity [8] [9].

1.1.1. Logos

What is the logic?

Several perspectives across different scientific areas are focusing on sustainability. The idea beyond this study is to explore how to seek for this target – “the ability to sustain” [10].

To guarantee continuity there is a need to assure that the ecosystem is capable of pursue its own cycle, in a continuum process to the transition step. Despite the countless crises that Earth ecosystem is facing, the current biodiversity reveals that the systems continuously seek for equilibrium, potentiating recovery, with the aim of contributing to the evolution of its residents.

One case of species evolution is humanity. The Manageceneⁱⁱⁱ is revealing that humanity is increasing longevity tanks to needs and expectations management based on risk and opportunity analysis.

The human relation with natural cycle is indissociable and in crisis moments there is an ambidexterity of consequences. Based on this, since the human sense of community, the social protection is the baseline to assure human survival in vulnerable moments. Accept that there are threats, analyse the associated risks and manage the needs, in order to minimize human vulnerability during the different phases of the life cycle, allow humanity to have a commitment to sustainability.

The transition is implicit in any ecosystem, from an organism (i.e. person) to a social web (i.e. communities, systems of communities), and it is a fundamental step to perform an upgrade for the next level, necessary for coevolution. Leave a documented capital for future generations potentiate the possibility of understanding the origins, the trail and the premises to continue the human legacy. That’s why the capital preservation, from material to immaterial, is so important [11].

The Sustainable Development Goals (SDG) is one of the well-known initiatives that seeks for sustainability, which comprises an agenda with several targets [12]. This agenda can be seen as an overview of humanity plan A. And what are the contingency plans?

There are several efforts to build different contingency plans, some of them seeking for the same goal – sustainability. Although the plan A still has a high margin for improvement, this current plan is in fact the baseline for contingency plans. There is a need to continue working on that to assure that the contingency plans work and can be reformulated whenever necessary or relevant.

Based on the presented logic, the target of this research is abductive, since intends to read current reality, based on a co-creation approach through (e)participation of actors, and contribute for the preservation of immaterial legacy through geroscience^{iv}.

1.1.2. Ethos

What is the ethic?

Social Protection, in parallel to other systems, is evolving according to the different variables of the life cycle and based on several foundations.

Currently human rights are widespread across the globe by several systems of belief. The Universal Declaration of Human Rights Declaration, promoted by United Nations, the European Pillar of Social Rights, and the United Nations Principles for Older Persons are some of the guidelines that expresses the goal of improving human interaction [13] [14] [15].

Based on this context, several questions arise from micro to macro scale, namely person-based, community-based and system-based questions.

Regarding the ethic domain there are countless questions to try to seek for answers, from data ethic design to communication ethic action. Based on this alignment from the theoretical vision, considering the established human rights promoted by UN, to pragmatic form, based on human strategies of socialization, the equity is a well-known principle of the social agenda, a common target shared by different organizations and aligned with the coevolutionary social sustainability trail [12] [13].

1.1.3. Pathos

What are the programmes?

To attain a coevolutionary social sustainability trail based on equity principle, the geroscience can provide relevant insights since is the science that have the target of understanding all life cycle from a human-centred vision [10]. The human legacy, from origin to constructs left to nourish the future, is the treasure to preserve.

Several perspectives and actions coexist across the globe as regards to seniors, the masters of life cycle. Besides SDG, that has the intention of collecting data in a disaggregated form, namely by age, allowing the analysis of different phases of life cycle, the United Nations Decade of Healthy Ageing and the Green Paper on Ageing, are oriented initiatives regarding the last phase of human cycle [12] [16] [17]. Concerning the programmes, focusing on the country of the present study – Portugal – the Portuguese Active and Healthy Aging Action Plan 2023-2026^v is one of several inputs for the construction of the presented framework [18].

1.2. Communication

Communication is crucial for human coevolution and the trigger for sustainability.

The communication process integrates several phases, where information is the baseline. To start this process the communication actors can increase the performance by seeking for an overview and recommendations for action, namely for interaction based on virtual reality [19].

The virtual communication is based on the primary activation of 2 senses - visual and auditory – while the physical communication can benefit from the activation of the 5 senses. On the other hand, the power of virtual tools is increasing and today it is easier and quicker to first demonstrate big ideas on screen – virtual reality - than on physical reality.

But there are several challenges regarding virtual communication. The accessibility, digital equity and data ethic are some of them. These matters are currently on the agenda of several organizations. Several approaches are being studied, from qualitative to quantitative, such as reports, indexes and impact assessments.

Focusing on geroscience, physical, sensory and cognitive impairment are variables to manage because there are limitations to consider in both interactions, physical and virtual. Accessibility is a strategy to ensure that information reach everyone capable of process information and give feedback.

There are different approaches, strategies and tools to communicate with people with simple or complex needs. A human-centred communication can be an approach that fits every individual based on adjusted content, accessible information, comprehension, feedback and active participation [21] [22] [23] [24] [25].

1.3. Research question

Based on the presented overview, with the aim of pursue sustainability based on equity principle, through a participatory approach, several questions arise. A condensed question that goes from the gap to the expected solution is:

“What synergies can we explore to improve human communication?”

2. Research design

The research question of the present study is generalist which shows that the research design of this study is adaptative to other research areas, besides geroscience.

Based on an empirical background, solidified by theoretical perspectives, to interpret correctly the message 5 intrinsic components of life cycle were considered [6] [5] [7] [26] [27] [28].

Figure 1: A theoretical cyclical algorithm for coevolutionary social sustainability – RNOET approach (created by the author) based on insights of the crossover of empirical background and of literature review

In order to shape the wheel, a workflow was defined, as presented on the following table (Table 1).

Table 1: Workflow of methodology

Structure	Baseline	Method	Strategy
Idea	Sustainability (Transition heuristics / Communication / Participatory approaches / Digital equity/divide)	Crossover through mind map based on empirical background and literature review	Scoping review for definition of domains, conformity requirements checklist and values
Input	Ethic (Human rights / Social Rights / Older persons principles)		
Process	Programmes (United Nations Decade of Healthy Ageing / Green Paper on Ageing / Portuguese Active and Healthy Aging Action Plan)		

The idea of this project started with the empirical background based on researcher professional experience on social organizations which led to fruition through a research proposal submission to Portuguese Foundation for Science and Technology^{vi} [29].

The inputs were selected considering the baseline for social protection – ethic – and for that an overview of several perspectives was considered.

The current expressed needs and expectations of social actors, namely regarding sustainability and equity, are the baseline for the presented motivation.

For the literature review, premises of Prisma-ScR were the inspiration for a scoping review. The process is not restricted to the associated guidelines [10]. Regarding the scientific literature review, the WebScience, SCOPUS, Google Scholar, Engineering Village were databases consulted. Scientific publications written in English were the eligibility criteria. To perform organizations’ documentation review, the research focused on public documents, such as legislation, standards and orientations, from recognized organizations, written in English and Portuguese.

The inclusion criteria for analysis were databases filters based on “open access”, and “relevance” according to the selected databases, and, in specific cases, on “review”.

Regarding the programme, that is oriented to geroscience, is a component of the project cycle based on the idea of pursuing sustainability, that uses ethic as resource to feed the generator and recognises transition as a relevant part of every life cycle.

Based on the presented overview, the research design of this study, figure 2, focus on phase 2 – Ethos.

Figure 2: Research design (created by the author)

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Ethics

3.1.1. Domains

To follow the study vision, in accordance with UN philosophy “leave no one behind”, the Human rights and Elderly principles were considered as a baseline for the ethic domains. To concretize that, a crossover approach were carried out, based on the intersection of life cycle heuristics, Maslow's hierarchy of needs, morality foundations and basic principles of human rights monitoring [5] [6] [7] [28] [30].

The 5 selected domains for the ethical overview were:

Figure 3: A perspective of domains of ethic (created by the author) based based on insights of crossover of empirical background and of literature review

3.1.2. Conformity requirements

Based on literature review, with the purpose of prepare an ethical interaction with actors of the (e)participatory approach, a checklist of requirements that integrates different approaches, guidelines and standards was carried out. This checklist intends to be a tool for measure conformity with the selected requirements, which also aims to be an evolutionary tool. Given a high range of inputs, the conformity requirements were divided into 5 domains, namely human interaction, project, data, communication and transition.

3.1.2.1. Human interaction

The baseline for an ethical human interaction is the consideration of ethical principles, such as promoted by Universal Declaration of Human Rights Declaration and United Nations Principles for Older Persons, that are the foundations for the project values definition [13] [15].

To pursue the previous widespread principles there are several guidelines to ensure an ethical interaction with different actors. The selected guidelines integrate international initiatives, organizational and literature requirements, pursuing the baseline of equity and protection by design, figure 4 [30] [31] [32] [33] [34] [35] [36] [37].

Figure 4: Conformity requirements for human interaction (made by the author)

- **Vision, values and mission**

To start an in loco (e)participatory research the communication of the intention is the 1st step of the protocol. For that the presentation of the vision, the values and mission were defined as a task [26] [38] [39] [40] [41] [42] [43] [44].

- **Reciprocity / Consent**

Acceptance to participate on action research depends on the efficiency of communication about the purpose and the perception of aggregate value that can be achieved for both sides, firstly researcher and actors, as directed participants, and then the entire associated ecosystem. To clarify the commitment the reciprocity approach is the baseline. To put into formal action a consent document or recording are options and can integrate a range of premises, namely purpose, requirements, rights, recording operations, data protection, among other requirements defined as relevant for both parts [26] [43] [45] [46] [47].

- **Confidentiality**

The confidentiality requirement is part of the checklist because it is a human right and also a need/expectation expressed by several organizations, based on widely disseminated data protection guidelines. To assure this requirement from the beginning an encoding process is one of the strategies to guarantee the anonymisation of participants [31] [32] [46] [47].

- **Aptitude**

To perform an in loco work respecting the needs and expectations of the actors there is a need for definition of boundaries. These boundaries are important to limit how far the research can go with a transparent transaction. Several conditions can be considered, starting with 5 senses to efficient communication. Considering the target group – seniors – in which comorbidities are more expectable, an aptitude evaluation are the baseline to guarantee that there is no substantial cognitive impairment that compromises the communication efficiency based on two-way dialogue [22] [23] [48] [49] [50] [51].

- **Accessibility**

According to United Nation Global Principles for Information Integrity and with the aim of call researchers and civil society for action, some recommendations are suggested to be followed to preserve information integrity, namely: collaboration, ethical standards, open access and inclusive research [52].

Regarding to inclusive research, to put the recommendations into practice, based on aptitude analysis, adaptation of the strategies can be a technique to reach everyone eligible regardless the limitations initially anticipated. For that a study of the options available can be performed and, for those that are self-determined, freedom of choice is a right to guarantee [19] [53].

3.1.2.2. Project

Regarding the project, several inputs were analysed. The selected requirements integrate the needs expressed by Sustainable Development Goals, United Nations Decade of Healthy Ageing, Portuguese Active and Healthy Aging Action Plan 2023-2026, Portuguese Foundation for Science and Technology funding associated to a scholarship programme, among other requirements considered relevant for the study [12] [16] [18] [29].

3.1.2.3. Data

Concerning data requirements, a data management plan was created for this project. This plan intends to pursue a commitment to personal data protection, open data and interoperability [26] [47] [54]. In this study, data ethic is a process that is documented by metadata.

3.1.2.4. Communication

To implement in loco strategies to establish a human communication in an efficient manner, an (e)Participation design is the defined baseline for action research. The metainformation is an in-progress output that is an auditable capital, that belongs to communication ethic process.

3.1.2.5. Transition

To guarantee continuous improvement a crossover of approaches that integrates the (e)Participation design is a strategy to ensure a continuity plan. The strategy comprises an (e)participation research through a community-based (e)platform.

The theoretical structure for the cyclical algorithm that expresses the conformity requirements is presented on figure 5.

Figure 5: Conformity requirements theoretical structure
(created by the author)

3.1.3. Values

The presented overview from domains to conformity requirements are the premises for the definition of the values. As expressed before, equity is the baseline of project vision - sustainability. Spirality (based on life cycle heuristic), multigenerationality, win-win transaction and value creation are the interconnected and subsequent values to reach the project mission.

The registration of the trail and the value generated, which means the preservation of capital legacy, is important to communicate that to future generations to allow a clear interpretation of the obstacles that have been transposed and the progress that was made during the life course.

3.2. Hybrid platforms for equity

Social participation can be operationalized through a co-creation hybrid approach, physical and virtual participation – (e)participation.

Based on this premise, a human-centred approach for accessible information and community-based (e)participation are the defined strategies to improve communication, by both interactions (physical and virtual). These communicational strategies were developed during the Managecene, expressing that lessons learned from the past are always valuable inputs for human daily routines and for the construction of the future.

To start a strategic plan for community-based (e)participation, promoting self-consciousness for self-literacy visioning sustainability, there is a need of recognising and analysing the risks.

Both interactions entail data ethic risks, such as personal data protection, which is the baseline for safety. This issue has a close interaction in all phases of life cycle, and if the needs are not managed correctly can impact survival instincts and therefore social protection.

To promote coevolution, digital equity can enhance information integrity and communication efficiency, which in practice corresponds to an iterative trial with several domains. Many approaches coexist, revealing that access, interest, literacy, fair transaction and sustainable oriented are domains to be considered [11].

The access domain integrates infrastructures and digital services, namely hardware (equipment), software (interoperability) and internet (connectivity). The data protection and interaction between sender/receiver are common variables to several domains [55] [56] [57] [58] [59] [60].

Focusing on geroscience, gerontechnology^{vii} can benefit from the crossover of several approaches to guarantee accessible communication and (e)participation [61] [62].

Today there is a high range of assistive intelligent technologies. Regarding the hardware some of them include wearable, handheld devices, mobility aids, voice activated assistants, distributed systems, specific robots [63]. As regard to software, mobile apps, eplatforms, electronic records, remote monitoring systems and other communication tools are available and evolving [64].

As regard to interest, several variables need to be addressed to achieve digital equity [55].

Fair transaction is a condition to promote cooperation and (e)communities networks are a strategy to face challenges and potentiate (e)inclusion [65] [66] [67].

(e)Participation methods are a strategy for identification of gaps of digital equity, understand the users' needs and a trial for adjust the approaches to that needs and also to the expectations [68] [69] [70].

An operational (e)platform can promote active aging in several dimensions, by providing accessibility and assistance to people in need [71] [72].

Community-based (e)participation is an approach for an acceleration of self-consciousness to promote self-literacy and pursue social transition to seek for sustainability. This can be promoted by a community-based transition heuristic through an accessible communication, based on data literacy, standard designs and interoperable platforms [11].

Self-literacy is an approach in expansion based on generation 5.0 opportunities, that can integrate geroscience as a multiobjective trail based on life cycle view and learning [8].

4. Conclusions

To put into practice a human-centred approach, the baseline of 5th generation, to promote sustainable communities, a risk and opportunity analysis is a necessary and continuous process to feed geroscience, in order to understand the real needs and expectations of population. The consultation and participation approach is an ethical model because there is a reciprocity mechanism, allowing feedback by conscious choice and not by assumed expected behaviour, based on track record to date, because the life cycle change and people have the option of adapt according to that.

Conscious decision making starts with a plan for data acquisition, using equity and protection by design as a baseline.

To concretize a human-centred with ethic and pursue the mission of coevolutionary social sustainability, a structured (e)participation approach was selected to carry out this study.

Community-based social protection is an outcome-oriented approach that can be achieved from human-centred accessible information through an (e)platform, powered by a community-based (e)participation.

This community-based research intends to put senior (e)communities as transition agents, using (e)participation as a process for sustainable management and promote self-consciousness, based on science-based literacy, to inspire self-literacy, contributing for conscious decision-making.

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ⁱ (e)participation – comprises physical and virtual participation

ⁱⁱ Equity –defined as the quality of being fair or impartial. In practice, equity consists in non-discrimination / non-rejection of no one, as promoted by United Nations – “Leave no one behind” [73]

ⁱⁱⁱ Managecene – Era of evolution of humanity were humans started to shape the planet according to their needs and expectations (based on Homogenocene / Antropocene) [74]

^{iv} Geroscience – the science that study the human life cycle based on an integrated overview and oriented to a multigeneracional approach, intending to preserve human legacy for future generations [10].

^v Portuguese Active and Healthy Aging Action Plan 2023-2026 - “Plano de Ação do Envelhecimento Ativo e Saudável 2023-2026”

^{vi} Portuguese Foundation for Science and Technology – “Fundação para a Ciência e a Tecnologia”

^{vii} Gerontechnology – the technology adjusted to the impairment contracted during the life cycle